

Tolerances on wavefront aberrations

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The purpose of the present note is to study the sensitivity of the HIPPARCOS instrument to various kinds of wavefront deformations. Assuming that all deformations are much smaller than the wavelength of light, one finds quite simple analytical expressions for the perturbations on the ideal optical transfer function (OTF), viz. the deterioration of the modulation transfer function (MTF) and production of a non-zero phase transfer function (PTF). In order to produce some tentative tolerances on "acceptable" wavefront aberrations, two criteria will be applied. Firstly, the actual MTF at the fundamental spatial frequency of the grid should be at least 95 % of the ideal (diffraction-limited) MTF at that frequency. The motivation for this criterion is that the statistical mean error of the timing of the modulated signal is roughly inversely proportional to the MTF. Secondly, the PTF should be such that the differential displacement (again at the first harmonic of the grid) of two stars of widely different spectral types is less than 2 marcsec.

Theory: the OTF in terms of wavefront errors

Let $\vec{x} = (y, z)$ be a vector in the entrance pupil plane with origin at the optical axis, and let $H(\vec{x})$ be the characteristic function of the pupil (i.e. $H = 1$ if $\vec{x}$ is inside the pupil area, otherwise $H = 0$). The ideal (aberration-free) OTF is then (AML Report Vol. I, Section 2.4)

$$T_o(\vec{u}) = \iint H(\vec{x})H(\vec{x} - \vec{u}) d\vec{x}, \quad (1)$$

i.e. simply the area of $A(\vec{u}) = H(\vec{x}) \cap H(\vec{x} - \vec{u})$, the overlapping parts of $H(\vec{x})$ and $H(\vec{x} - \vec{u})$, Figure 1. If aberrations are present, corresponding to a wavefront error (optical path difference) $\delta(\vec{x})$ at a point $\vec{x}$ in the pupil, the OTF becomes

$$T_\lambda(\vec{u}) = \iint_{A(\vec{u})} \exp\left\{ik\left[\delta(\vec{x}) - \delta(\vec{x} - \vec{u})\right]\right\} d\vec{x}, \quad (2)$$

where $k = 2\pi/\lambda$. The MTF $[M_\lambda(\vec{u})]$ and the PTF $[P_\lambda(\vec{u})]$ are the modulus and argument of the OTF, respectively; hence

$$M_\lambda(\vec{u}) \cos P_\lambda(\vec{u}) = \text{Re}[T_\lambda(\vec{u})] = \iint_{A(\vec{u})} \cos\left[k\delta(\vec{x}) - k\delta(\vec{x} - \vec{u})\right] d\vec{x}, \quad (3)$$

$$M_\lambda(\vec{u}) \sin P_\lambda(\vec{u}) = \text{Im}[T_\lambda(\vec{u})] = \iint_{A(\vec{u})} \sin\left[k\delta(\vec{x}) - k\delta(\vec{x} - \vec{u})\right] d\vec{x}. \quad (4)$$

Provided that $|\delta(x)| \ll \lambda$, we may use the small-angle approximations $\sin x \simeq x$ and $\cos x \simeq 1 - x^2/2$ to obtain

$$\text{Re}[T_\lambda(\vec{u})] = T_o(\vec{u}) \left\{ 1 - \frac{1}{2} k^2 \langle [\delta(\vec{x}) - \delta(\vec{x} - \vec{u})]^2 \rangle_{A(\vec{u})} \right\}, \quad (5)$$

$$\text{Im}[T_\lambda(\vec{u})] = T_o(\vec{u}) k \langle \delta(\vec{x}) - \delta(\vec{x} - \vec{u}) \rangle_{A(\vec{u})}, \quad (6)$$

where $\langle \cdot \rangle_{A(\vec{u})}$ denotes an average over the area $A(\vec{u})$. Putting $\Delta \equiv \delta(\vec{x}) - \delta(\vec{x} - \vec{u})$ for brevity, we find

$$\begin{aligned} M_\lambda(\vec{u}) &= \left\{ \text{Re}^2[T_\lambda(\vec{u})] + \text{Im}^2[T_\lambda(\vec{u})] \right\}^{\frac{1}{2}} = \\ &= T_o(u) \left\{ 1 - k^2 \langle \Delta^2 \rangle + k^4 \langle \Delta^2 \rangle^2 + k^2 \langle \Delta \rangle^2 \right\}^{\frac{1}{2}} \simeq \\ &\simeq T_o(u) \left\{ 1 - \frac{1}{2} k^2 \left[\langle \Delta^2 \rangle - \langle \Delta \rangle^2 \right] \right\}. \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

Now $\langle \Delta^2 \rangle - \langle \Delta \rangle^2$ is of course the mean square deviation of Δ from its average over $A(\vec{u})$. If $\delta(\vec{x})$ is a random gaussian function of variance δ_{rms}^2 and uncorrelated over a separation equal to $\vec{u}$, we have $\langle \Delta^2 \rangle - \langle \Delta \rangle^2 = 2\delta_{\text{rms}}^2$ and hence the formula (cf. Born and Wolf, 1970, 9.1.3)

$$M_\lambda(\vec{u}) = T_o(\vec{u}) \left[1 - 4\pi^2 (\delta_{\text{rms}}/\lambda)^2 \right]. \quad (8)$$

Thus, in order to have $M_\lambda(\vec{u})/T_o(\vec{u}) \geq 0.95$, we must have $\delta_{\text{rms}}/\lambda \leq 0.0356$, i.e. $\delta_{\text{rms}} \leq \lambda/28 \simeq 17$ nm, since $\lambda_{\text{eff}} = 480$ nm for a star of intermediate spectral type.

For the PTF we find to first order

$$P_{\lambda}(\vec{u}) = k \langle \delta(\vec{x}) - \delta(\vec{x} - \vec{u}) \rangle_{A(\vec{u})}. \quad (9)$$

Application to the baseline instrument

Let s be the grid period in radians and D the length of the aperture diameter (baseline is $D = 0.25$ m and $s = 1.1'' = 5.333 \cdot 10^{-6}$ rad). Only the OTF normal to the slits is of interest ($u_z = 0$), so we have $\vec{u} = u\hat{y}$, where $\hat{y}$ is the unit vector normal to the slits. The spatial frequencies of the grid transmittance are, moreover, $u = n\lambda/s$, where $n = 0, 1, 2, \dots$ for the different harmonics. Since the OTF is strictly zero for $u < D$, we have in reality $n_{\max} = \text{entier}(sD/\lambda)$ harmonics, and the OTF has to be computed only at the $n_{\max}$ points $\vec{u} = (n\lambda/s)\hat{y}$.

The phase shift $P_{\lambda}(\vec{u})$ of the Fourier component of the image having spatial frequency u/λ rad $^{-1}$ in the image plane, corresponds to a linear displacement $(ku)^{-1}P_{\lambda}(\vec{u})$ rad. The displacement of the Fourier component corresponding to the n :th harmonic of the grid is then

$$\Delta_n(\lambda) = \frac{s}{2\lambda n} P_{\lambda}(n\lambda/s), \quad (10)$$

or, using eq. (9),

$$\Delta_n(\lambda) = \frac{s}{n\lambda} \langle \delta(\vec{x}) - \delta(\vec{x} - \frac{n\lambda}{s}\hat{y}) \rangle_{A(n\lambda/s.\hat{y})}. \quad (11)$$

Consider for instance a wavefront tilted a small angle α , $\delta(x) = \delta_0 + \alpha y$. Then $\delta(x) - \delta(x - n\lambda/s.\hat{y}) = \alpha n\lambda/s$ and $\Delta_n(\lambda) = \alpha$; the wavefront tilt produces a perfectly achromatic image displacement by the same angle, as expected. For non-linear asymmetric wavefront errors, however, it is easy to see that the resulting displacement $\Delta_n(\lambda)$ will in general depend on $n\lambda$, which is the undesirable chromaticity we want to restrict.

Take a rectangular pupil of length D and width E , with a rectangular central obstruction $\eta D \times \eta E$ (Figure 2). Then it is easy to see that the overlapping area $A(u\hat{y})$ is simply a rectangle:

$$\vec{x} \in A(u\hat{y}) \Leftrightarrow \left(u - \frac{D}{2} \leq y \leq \frac{D}{2}\right) \wedge (\eta E \leq z \leq E), \quad (12)$$

provided that $\frac{1}{2}(1 - \eta) \leq u/D \leq \eta$. For the baseline case, $s = 1.1''$, $D = 0.25$ m, and $\eta = 0.45$, the latter condition is equivalent to

$$367 \text{ nm} \leq n\lambda \leq 600 \text{ nm}. \quad (13)$$

Since the effective wavelength range of the instrument (glass relay optics + S-20 photocathode) is about 350 - 650 nm, we conclude that, for the first harmonic of the modulated signal ($n = 1$), the average in eq. (11) may be taken over the ~~width~~ rectangular domain (12).

Introducing the averaged wavefront error along the perpendicular coordinate (z),

$$\xi(y) \equiv \frac{2}{E} \int_{E/2}^E \delta(y, z) dz, \quad (14)$$

we find that the displacement of the first harmonic is

$$\Delta_1(\lambda) = \frac{s}{\lambda} \frac{1}{D - \lambda/s} \int_{\lambda/s - D/2}^{D/2} \left[\xi(y) - \xi\left(y - \frac{\lambda}{s}\right) \right] dy. \quad (15)$$

In the next two sections we compute the differential displacement of two stars of different spectral types, assuming polynomial and trigonometric representations of $\xi(y)$. The averaging with respect to wavelength is made assuming a gaussian sensitivity curve, $S(\lambda) \propto \exp\left[-(\lambda - \lambda_0)^2 / 2\Delta\lambda^2\right]$. The parameters λ_0 and $\Delta\lambda$ are given in Table 1.

Table 1. Effective wavelength (λ_0) and bandwidth ($\Delta\lambda = 1$ s.d.) for stars of various spectral types. A short-wavelength cut-off at about 325 nm is assumed; the long-wavelength cut-off is determined by the photocathode sensitivity.

Sp	B2	A1	F0	F7	G8	K3	K6	M2	
B - V	-.25	.00	.25	.50	.75	1.00	1.25	1.50	
S-20	λ_0 (nm)	432	457	471	484	505	526	551	576
	$\Delta\lambda$ (nm)	82	84	88	91	94	97	95	92
Bialkali	λ_0 (nm)	412	426	437	445	459	471	482	488
	$\Delta\lambda$ (nm)	61	62	61	60	60	59	59	58

Polynomial representation of $\xi(y)$

Assume $\xi(y)$ is a polynomial of order m in y .

$$\xi(y) = \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} c_m \cdot (2y/D)^m, \quad (16)$$

so that c_m is the magnitude of each term at the extreme points ($y = \pm D/2$). Since (15) is linear in $\xi(y)$, we may consider each term of (16) separately. Eq. (15) gives immediately

$$\Delta_1(\lambda) = \begin{cases} (m+1)^{-1} c_m / D \cdot \frac{1 - (1 - 2u/D)^{m+1}}{(u/D)(1 - u/D)} & (m \text{ odd}); \\ 0 & (m \text{ even}). \end{cases} \quad (17)$$

Thus, only asymmetric aberrations (m odd) contribute to the image displacement; symmetric aberrations affect only the MTF.

A more remarkable thing becomes apparent if we introduce the new variable $v = 1 - 2u/D$; then, for odd m ,

$$\begin{aligned}\Delta_1(\lambda) &= \frac{4}{m+1} \frac{c_m}{D} \frac{1 - v^{m+1}}{1 - v^2} = \\ &= \frac{4}{m+1} \frac{c_m}{D} (1 + v^2 + v^4 + \dots + v^{m-1}).\end{aligned}\quad (18)$$

Thus $\Delta_1(\lambda)$ is symmetric around $v = 0$, corresponding to $u = D/2$, and, moreover,

$$\left. \frac{\partial}{\partial \lambda} \Delta_1(\lambda) \right|_{u=D/2} = 0. \quad (19)$$

Since the chromaticity depends more or less on this derivative, we conclude that chromaticity may be eliminated, or at least strongly suppressed, by selecting a grid period satisfying $u = D/2$ or

$$s = 2\lambda_0/D. \quad (20)$$

With typically $\lambda_0 = 480$ nm (S-20) this yields $s = 0.79''$. This corresponds to a normalized spatial frequency $\xi = 0.60$ with respect to a reference wavelength 400 nm, in good agreement with the computations by Vaghi (MAD Working Paper No. 95, p. 4), who finds minimum chromaticity for normalized spatial frequencies 0.5 - 0.6.

While (20) is in fact also the theoretically optimum grid period from the point of view of statistical accuracy of single-star observations, it is not suitable for double-star observations because the second harmonic of the modulated signal is very weak. In practice we must have $s \approx 1.1''$, corresponding to $u/D \approx 0.25 - 0.50$ depending on λ .

We shall define chromaticity as the differential displacement $\Delta_1(B2) - \Delta_1(K3)$ of two stars of spectral type B2 and K3, using the gaussian sensitivity parameters in Table 1 (S-20 cathode). The averaging over λ of v^2 , v^4 , etc. yields

$$\overline{v^2} = v_0^2 + \Delta v^2, \quad \overline{v^4} = v_0^4 + 6v_0^2 \Delta v^2 + 3\Delta v^4, \quad \text{etc.}, \quad (21)$$

where $v_0 = 1 - 2\lambda_0/sD$ and $\Delta v = 2\Delta\lambda/sD$. Carrying out the numerical computations we find

$$\Delta_1(B2) - \Delta_1(K3) = 0.079 \frac{c_3}{D} + 0.068 \frac{c_5}{D} + 0.054 \frac{c_7}{D} + 0.045 \frac{c_9}{D} + \sum_{\substack{m=11 \\ \text{(odd)}}}^{\infty} \frac{0.46}{m+1} \frac{c_m}{D}. \quad (22)$$

Since 2 marcsec over a distance $D = 0.25$ m makes 2.4 nm, we have (taking each term separately) the tolerances corresponding to $|\Delta_1(B2) - \Delta_1(K3)| \leq 2$ marcsec:

$$\begin{aligned} |c_3| &\leq 30 \text{ nm}, \\ |c_5| &\leq 35 \text{ nm}, \\ |c_7| &\leq 45 \text{ nm, etc.} \end{aligned} \quad (23)$$

Trigonometric representation of $\xi(y)$

When it comes to relatively small-scale wavefront deformations, it is more convenient to use trigonometric representations of $\xi(y)$. Consider again only one component

$$\xi(y) = A \cos \omega x + B \sin \omega x. \quad (24)$$

Eq. (15) gives

$$\Delta_1(\lambda) = B \frac{2s}{\omega \lambda (D - \lambda/s)} \left\{ \cos \left[\frac{1}{2} \omega (D - 2\lambda/s) \right] - \cos \left(\frac{1}{2} \omega D \right) \right\}. \quad (25)$$

Introducing again the variable $v = 1 - 2\lambda/sD$ and the period (wavelength) of the deformation $\Lambda = 2\pi/\omega$, we find

$$\Delta_1(\lambda) = \frac{B}{D} (\pi D/\Lambda)^{-1} (1 - v^2)^{-1} \left[\cos(v\pi D/\Lambda) - \cos(\pi D/\Lambda) \right]. \quad (26)$$

Again it is clear that the symmetric part of the aberration [cosine component in (24)] produces no displacement, and that $\Delta_1(\lambda)$ is symmetric with respect to v .

Eq. (26) may be approximately averaged with respect to λ by neglecting the smooth variation of $(1 - v^2)^{-1}$ with λ and using the relation

$$\overline{\cos(av)} = \cos(av_0) \exp(-\frac{1}{2} a^2 \Delta v^2) \quad (27)$$

when v is normally distributed with mean v_0 and s.d. Δv .
Thus

$$\Delta_1(\text{Sp}) = \frac{B}{D} \frac{(\pi D/\lambda)^{-1}}{1 - v_0^2} \left[e^{-\frac{1}{2} v^2 (\pi D/\lambda)^2} \cos(v_0 \pi D/\lambda) - \cos(\pi D/\lambda) \right] \dots \quad (28)$$

The quantity $\frac{D}{B} [\Delta_1(B2) - \Delta_2(K3)]$, which gives the chromaticity in units of the angle B/D , has been computed as a function of the spatial frequency D/λ of the wavefront aberration (Figure 3). It turns out that the most critical spatial frequency is $D/\lambda \simeq 1.8$, for which the chromaticity is $\simeq 0.5 B/D$. Thus, to keep the chromaticity below 2 marcsec it is required that the amplitude of this deformation component is less than $B \simeq 5 \text{ nm}$ (or $\lambda/100$).

At spatial frequencies above $D/\lambda \simeq 3$ the chromaticity is suppressed (at least with S-20 cathode) by the wavelength averaging; however, a residual effect remains thanks to the factor $(1 - v_0^2)^{-1}$ in (28). The typical (rms) chromaticity at high frequencies is about $\pm 0.35(B/D)(D/\lambda)^{-1}$ (dashed curves). In fact, for $D/\lambda \geq 3.5$ the deterioration of MTF is a more serious problem than chromaticity, since 2 marcsec chromaticity at $D/\lambda = 3.5$ requires an amplitude $B = 24 \text{ nm}$, for which $\delta_{\text{rms}} = 17 \text{ nm}$ and the MTF is decreased by 5 %.

Thus we arrive at the following tentative specification of wavefront error tolerances:

- (1) the overall accuracy should be better than 17 nm rms, or $\lambda/37$ at $\lambda = 633 \text{ nm}$;
- (2) for the critical frequency range of spatial deformations, $D/\lambda \simeq 0.7$ to 3.0, we have the additional restriction that the amplitude of the wavefront deformation should not exceed 5 nm.

Effects of chromaticity on scientific data

Calibration

It has been stated above that 2 marcsec is an acceptable level of chromaticity. Because of the "systematic" nature of the effect this tolerance may appear rather liberal. In this section we discuss how chromaticity is likely to affect the final astrometric data and possible means of calibrating the effect.

To begin with it should be noted however that the displacements of the first and second harmonics of the modulated signal tend to compensate each other, so it is likely the the effective chromaticity is substantially less than $\Delta_1(B2) - \Delta_1(K3)$. This is a consequence of the symmetry of (26) around $v = 0$. Putting $v_n = 1 - 2n\lambda/sD$ for the n :th harmonic, it follows that, at a certain wavelength satisfying $v_1 = -v_2$ (viz. $\lambda = sD/3 = 444$ nm), we have $\Delta_1(\lambda) = \Delta_2(\lambda)$. Moreover, since $dv_n/d\lambda = -2n/sD$,

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial \lambda} \Delta_2(\lambda) = -2 \frac{\partial}{\partial \lambda} \Delta_1(\lambda). \quad (29)$$

By taking a suitably weighted average of the phases of the two harmonics it is then possible to reduce chromaticity considerably. An optimum estimator will in fact tend to give the first harmonic about twice the weight of the second (for typical modulation coefficients), which is precisely what is needed to eliminate chromaticity. This requires however that the function $\xi(y)$ is well defined and the same for the two harmonics; in reality this may not be the case since, for the second harmonic, the overlapping area $A(\vec{u})$ is no longer the simple rectangle assumed above. At any rate a comparison of the two harmonics will provide useful information about chromaticity.

In order that residual chromaticity should be successfully eliminated in the data reduction procedure, it is necessary that (a) the effect is to a large part constant in time (preferably throughout the mission), (b) the effect is constant or slowly varying within the field of view, and (c) the effect is statistically separable from the astrometric parameters and attitude deviations. We shall discuss the three factors in turn.

Possible reasons for time variability may be ageing and thermal deformations. Although we have no data on ageing effects of ceramic glasses, it seems rather unlikely that they could produce variable deformations at the critical spatial frequencies - around $D/\lambda = 2$. It is not unreasonable to think however that the thermostatic control of the mirrors may set up travelling waves in the mirrors having the right wavelength (depending on conductivity and frequency of thermostatic switching). In the absolute worst case we may have a temperature amplitude of 0.05 K, which with a mirror thickness of 100 mm gives a deformation amplitude of 0.15 nm (expansion coefficient $3 \cdot 10^{-8} \text{ K}^{-1}$ for ULE glass) and a variation of chromaticity by ± 0.13 marcsec. Thermal deformation of the supporting structure appears to be sufficiently under control. So there are reasons to believe that any chromaticity the instrument will have during operation is mainly due to imperfections of the mirror manufacturing and optical alignment and is essentially constant with time.

Variations of chromaticity across the FOV must be due to the function $\delta(\vec{x})$ being different as seen from different points of the FOV. If the entrance pupil is defined close to the complex mirror, it is clear that any wavefront aberration originating from the complex mirror will be independent of the position in the FOV. This is not so however for the primary and (in particular) secondary mirror, where the illuminated part is slightly shifted depending on position in the FOV. Consider the secondary mirror as the most critical element. From the gaussian solution of the baseline instrument it follows that the length of the illuminated area of the secondary (from a point source), i.e. the linear distance corresponding to D at the entrance pupil, is 78.8 mm,

and that the illumination is shifted a distance 1110α mm for a point source an angle α (rad) from the optical axis. Assume that there is a ~~small~~ sinusoidal deformation of the secondary corresponding to a wavefront error for a point-source on the optical axis

$$\varepsilon_0(y) = A \sin(2\pi y/\Lambda + \varphi), \quad (30)$$

where, as before, y is the linear coordinate in the entrance pupil.

For a point source an angle α away from the optical axis the illuminated part of the secondary mirror has its centre at a point corresponding to the coordinate $y = (1110 \text{ mm}) / (78.8 \text{ mm}) \cdot D\alpha \approx 14.1 D\alpha$ at the entrance pupil; the wavefront deformation as seen from the point at α is therefore

$$\varepsilon_\alpha(y) = A \sin[2\pi(y - 14.1 D\alpha)/\Lambda + \varphi]. \quad (31)$$

The amplitude of the sine component of (31) is obviously

$$B = A \cos[\varphi + 2\pi(D/\Lambda) \cdot 14.1\alpha], \quad (32)$$

and the resulting chromaticity can be evaluated by means of Fig. 3.

Figure 4 shows some results for $A = 5$ nm and $\varphi = \pi/4$ (these are of course quite arbitrary figures chosen for illustration only). It is evident that deformations at the most critical spatial frequencies ($D/\Lambda \approx 2 \pm 1$) can only produce a smooth variation of chromaticity across the field,

while the high spatial frequencies which might produce "irregular" variations over the field are strongly suppressed by the averaging over $A(\vec{u})$ and λ shown by Fig. 3.

Therefore it seems probable that chromaticity, if not necessarily constant over the FOV, at least can be represented by a small set of parameters, e.g. the coefficients of a polynomial ($\ln \eta$ and ρ) of degree ≤ 3 . The effect may of course be entirely different for the two FOV's, but this is no severe complication since ~~the~~ each ~~star~~ star is regularly observed in both fields.

Moreover, if the observing strategy distributes the observing time on a particular star more or less evenly along the scanning direction of the FOV (η or y), the residual chromaticity will depend only on the perpendicular coordinate (ρ or z) and the number of colour-dependent distortion terms to be accurately determined is greatly reduced.

The separability of chromaticity from the astrometric parameters is most easily demonstrated by taking a particular example. Table 2 lists the essential coefficients of the observation equations for the astrometric parameters of a star at ecliptic coordinates $(\lambda, \beta) = (1.0, 0.5)$ rad (revolving scanning with sun/spin-axis angle 0.6 rad and $K=7.854$, total duration 2.5 yr). The significance of the observation equation coefficients c_{ji} (for the j :th astrometric parameter p_j , $j=1, 2, 3, 4, 5$, and the i :th observation epoch, $i=1, 2, \dots, 15$

Table 2. Observation equations for the astrometric parameters (example of "typical" case). $(\lambda, \beta) = (1.0, 0.5)$ rad, revolving angle $\delta = 0.6$ rad, $K = 7.854$, $\gamma = K \lambda_0 = 2\pi K(c + 1.25)$, τ = time in years reckoned from mid-epoch.

Obs. epoch no. (i)	Time τ (yr)	λ_0 (rad)	Coeff. of astrometric parameters				
			C_{1i} ($\Delta\lambda \cos\beta$)	C_{2i} ($\Delta\beta$)	C_{3i} ($\mu_\lambda \cos\beta$)	C_{4i} (μ_β)	C_{5i} (ω)
1	-0.900	2.198	-0.643	-0.765	+0.579	+0.689	-0.465
2	-0.847	2.530	+0.549	-0.837	-0.465	+0.709	+0.565
3	-0.792	2.880	-0.378	-0.925	+0.299	+0.733	-0.495
4	-0.375	5.500	-0.455	+0.891	+0.171	-0.334	+0.535
5	-0.312	5.895	+0.472	+0.881	-0.147	-0.275	-0.535
6	-0.266	6.182	-0.637	+0.772	+0.169	-0.205	+0.401
7	+0.116	8.581	-0.636	-0.772	-0.074	-0.090	-0.513
8	+0.175	8.952	+0.598	-0.801	+0.105	-0.140	+0.558
9	+0.224	9.259	-0.288	-0.958	-0.065	-0.215	-0.446
10	+0.548	11.300	+0.455	+0.889	+0.249	+0.487	-0.076
11	+0.641	11.883	-0.511	+0.859	-0.328	+0.551	+0.554
12	+0.712	12.325	+0.357	+0.933	+0.254	+0.664	-0.483
13	+0.132	14.965	-0.619	-0.787	-0.701	-0.891	-0.545
14	+0.197	15.376	+0.632	-0.777	+0.757	-0.930	+0.526
15	+0.238	15.634	-0.170	-0.985	-0.210	-0.219	-0.335

$$\sum_i C_{ji} = -1.274 \quad -2.382 \quad +0.593 \quad -0.466 \quad -0.794$$

$$\sum_i C_{ji}^2 = 3.945 \quad 11.055 \quad 2.084 \quad 5.944 \quad 3.547$$

$$\sum_i C_{ji} / \sum_i C_{ji}^2 = -0.323 \quad -0.215 \quad +0.285 \quad -0.078 \quad -0.224$$

in this case) is that the displacement in the y -direction of the star in the i th observation, due to the astrometric parameters, is

$$\Delta \eta_i = \sum_{j=1}^5 c_{ji} p_j \quad \Leftrightarrow \quad \underline{H} = \underline{C} \underline{P} \quad (32)$$

which is the essential part of the observation equation for this epoch. The least-squares solution is of course

$$\underline{P} = (\underline{C}^T \underline{C})^{-1} \underline{C}^T \underline{H}. \quad (33)$$

In fact, the observation equations in Table 2 are so well decorrelated that $(\underline{C}^T \underline{C})^{-1}$ is almost diagonal; hence, an approximate least-squares solution for the parameter p_j is simply

$$p_j = \left[\sum_i c_{ji}^2 \right]^{-1} \sum_i c_{ji} \Delta \eta_i. \quad (34)$$

Now suppose there is a constant bias Δ in all measurements of $\Delta \eta_i$, e.g. due to chromaticity. The bias of p_j is then

$$\Delta p_j = \left[\sum_i c_{ji} / \sum_i c_{ji}^2 \right] \cdot \Delta. \quad (35)$$

The factors $\sum_i c_{ji} / \sum_i c_{ji}^2$ are given at the bottom of Table 2; they are all numerically less than $1/3$. Thus, even if we take no precaution to calibrate or eliminate the chromaticity, a systematic effect on the 2 marcsec level in the Fov will be reduced to less than 1 marcsec in the final astrometric data. The sign of $\sum_i c_{ji} / \sum_i c_{ji}^2$ will generally be different for different stars on the sky, so it is not likely that e.g. the parallax zero point is systematically different for different spectral types, down to a level of a few

tenths of a marcsec.

In fact, a constant (but of course colour dependent) bias can be perfectly well eliminated in the reduction procedure, without knowing the effective colours of the stars, simply by introducing a sixth parameter p_6 ("colour") to each star, and taking the observation equation coefficient $c_{6i} = 1$. It can be shown that this procedure is equivalent to subtracting from each observation equation in Table 2, the "average" observation equation [n = number of observations (15)]

$$n^{-1} \sum_i \Delta \eta_i = n^{-1} \sum_i \sum_j c_{ji} p_j. \quad (36)$$

Clearly this gives a new set of "centred" coefficients $c'_{ji} = c_{ji} - n^{-1} \sum_i c_{ji}$ and we will have $\sum_i c'_{ji} / \sum_i c'^2_{ji} = 0$ and no influence of Δ on the astrometric parameters.

The variance factors are increased from $(\sum_i c_{ji}^2)^{-1}$ to $(\sum_i c'^2_{ji})^{-1} = [\sum_i c_{ji}^2 - n^{-1}(\sum_i c_{ji})^2]^{-1}$ or 0.2 - 3.5 % in the present example, showing that the penalty of introducing the colour parameter is only an increase of the mean errors of the other five parameters by less than 2 %.

If the colours of the stars are approximately known (which will be the case for practically all the stars), it is however better to modelise the chromaticity and determine colour-dependent field-distorsion terms as outlined above.

Figure 1. Definition of pupil function $H(\vec{x})$ and $A(\vec{u})$.

Figure 2. Shape and dimensions of entrance pupil.

Figure 3. Chromaticity $\Delta_1(B2) - \Delta_2(K3)$, in units of the angle B/D , as a function of the normalized frequency D/λ of the wavefront deformation $\xi(y) = B \sin(2\pi y D/\lambda)$.

